

Analysis of Respiration Induced Movements of the Upper Body in Different Breathing Patterns

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Abstract: Inferring respiratory parameters accurately from surface motion of the upper body has been a matter of research for many years. Advances in sensors and sensor technologies could soon allow smart clothing to reliably determine respiratory parameters. This study provides an overview of the locations and magnitudes of respiration induced movements of the upper body during different breathing patterns.

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I. Introduction

Scientific research has considered the determination of respiration parameters via surface movement on the upper body for many years. While the initial idea goes back to Konno and Mead [1] in the 1960s, there is still no wearable device commercially available that can infer respiratory parameters accurately from surface motion of the upper body. This paucity of development exists in spite of considerable interest in accurate respiratory measurements.

One approach shows potential to meet the objective. The optoelectronic plethysmography OEP [2] measures the surface motion of the upper body in high accuracy. It is based on an optical motion capture system with several cameras and reflective markers. Beside the costs of the measurement system, the main drawback of the OEP is the restriction to the measurement area between the cameras, which implies that the system is not wearable.

Due to the progress in the development of novel, improved and miniaturized sensors, wearable technologies are on the rise [3, 4]. This boost is evident in the ongoing development of improved smart clothing. Currently, smart clothing allows the determination of a couple of vital parameters, such as breathing- and heart frequencies. But smart clothing that can reliably and accurately measure tidal volumes is not yet available.

In this study, the respiration induced movements of the upper body are analysed, as these are decisive for the minimal complexity and localization of sensors in smart clothing items. While De Groote et al. [5] refer to the mean values, this study gives an overview of the magnitude of the maximal movements / displacements.

II. Methods

To analyse the movement of the upper body a motion capture system MoCap was implemented. Nine infrared

cameras (VICON Bonita B10, Firmware Version 404) were utilized in the MoCap (Bonita, VICON, Denver, CO). A total of 102 reflective MoCap markers were placed on a tight compression shirt (48 ventral, 18 lateral and 36 dorsal), which was worn during measurement by the subjects. The raw measurement data were processed and the spatial positions of the markers at each point in time were transferred to MATLAB (R2019a, The MathWorks, Natick, USA) by the VICON Nexus Software (Version 1.8.5.6 1009h, Vicon Motion Systems Ltd.). All further calculations were done in MATLAB. For each MoCap marker, the mean position during each respiratory pattern was calculated, and the displacement of the marker was determined by projecting the spatial positions on the main axis of the marker motion with respect to the mean position.

Different respiratory manoeuvres (normal spontaneous breathing NB, shallow breathing SB, maximal breaths MB, abdominal AB and chest breathing CB) were done by six subjects in sitting position. Details to the subjects can be found in Table 1. After one minute in each manoeuvre, the subjects did normal spontaneous breathing for 30 seconds as a recovery pause. Afterwards they were instructed to perform the next breathing pattern at the beginning of the next breath. Apart from the maximal breaths, the tidal volumes of the breathing pattern were chosen by the subjects themselves intuitively.

Table 1: Subjects

Subject	Height (m)	Weight (kg)	Gender	BMI (kg/m ²)	Age (years)
1	1.84	75	m	22.1	18
2	1.72	65	f	22.0	19
3	1.70	56	m	19.4	26
4	1.67	57	f	20.4	18
5	1.83	78	m	23.3	30
6	1.79	75	m	23.4	53

Figure 1: Maximal respiration induced displacement of the ventral upper body in different breathing patterns of subject 1. The top illustrations are scaled to the maximal values of the respective breathing pattern (normal spontaneous breathing NB, shallow breathing SB, maximal breaths MB, abdominal breathing AB and chest breathing CB), while the lower illustrations are based on the same data but scaled to the maximal displacement of MB. All measurements are presented as deviation from mean in mm.

III. Results and discussion

Figure 1 illustrates the different ventral displacements in magnitude and their location at the upper body in different breathing patterns - exemplarily shown based on subject 1. The dorsal movements are not shown here because they are negligible compared to the ventral ones. Table 2 shows the maximal displacements of the MoCap markers in each breathing pattern for all subjects.

This study is intended to give an overview of the magnitude of the movements. The values vary individually since the inhaled tidal volumes were chosen intuitively by the subjects themselves and because the distribution between chest and abdominal breathing differs individually in NB and SB.

Table 2: Result – Maximal displacements of the MoCap markers

Subject	Maximal displacement [mm]				
	NB	SB	MB	AB	CB
1	16.6	2.0	28.1	17.2	10.0
2	7.6	7.4	28.0	12.7	11.0
3	13.5	6.7	19.3	10.2	6.5
4	5.7	4.3	14.8	12.0	5.8
5	8.1	6.0	30.2	27.8	15.5
6	16.3	11.0	17.9	24.3	15.6

In MB displacements up to 31 mm can be found, while in SB only small displacements occurred (subject 1 showed maximal displacements in SB of only 2 mm). In NB maximal displacements of $11.3 \text{ mm} \pm 4.8 \text{ mm}$ were found amongst the six subjects, while in SB the movements are smaller ($6.2 \text{ mm} \pm 3.0 \text{ mm}$). The maximal displacements occurred in MB ($23.1 \text{ mm} \pm 6.5 \text{ mm}$), while in AB maximal movements of $17.4 \text{ mm} \pm 7.1 \text{ mm}$ can be found at the abdominal part of the upper body and in CB the displacements are smaller and distributed over the whole thorax (maximal displacements $10.7 \text{ mm} \pm 4.2 \text{ mm}$).

However, due to aging it can be expected that maximal displacements will vary for older people. Subject 6 showed reduced movement of the thorax and tended to abdominal breathing. Aging causes a reduction in bone quantity and

alterations in bone quality [6], which reduces flexibility of the rib cage. Variations in people with different body shapes, such as obese people would also be possible. Hence, this evaluation should be repeated in further studies with more participants, especially with regard to age and body shape.

IV. Conclusions

This study shows the respiration induced displacements of the upper body in different breathing patterns. Based on this data, the sensor location in smart textiles can be optimized.

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